

Alcohol As A Risk Factor and Serum Magnesium As A Prognostic Indicator in Critically Ill Patients

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ABSTRACT

INTRODUCTION: Alcohol consumption significantly impacts the health of critically ill patients in the form of altered immune mechanisms, altered mentation. Chronic Alcoholism can lead to malnutrition chronic diarrhoea and renal dysfunction leading to wasting of magnesium by the kidney causing hypomagnesaemia. Magnesium is cofactor for wide range of enzymes, transporters and nucleic acids and essential for normal neuromuscular activity. Critical illness is a state of ill health with vital organ dysfunction. Severity of Critical illness is assessed by APACHE II and also in the form of Duration of ICU stay and need of ventilation. **MATERIALS & METHODS:** Retrospective study by collecting data from MRD. **RESULTS:** There were 23.7% Alcoholics, 76.3% Non-alcoholic. Age, Sex similar in both Alcoholics 56.07, Non-alcoholic 59.7. Majority 61-70 years both Alcoholic 28.5% and Non-alcoholics 26.6%. Majority are males both 78.5%, 53.3%. Normomagnesemia alcoholics 21.4%, Non-alcoholic 70%. Hypomagnesaemia alcoholics 67.85%, Non-alcoholic 21.1%. Prevalence of Hypomagnesemia Alcoholics highly statistically significant, p-value is <0.001. Mean APACHE Alcoholics 23.5 ±6.88, Non-alcoholics 21.0 ± 7.41. Mean APACHE Hypomagnesemic Alcoholics 27.07 compared to 19.1 Non-alcoholics. Duration of ICU stay Alcoholics 4.75 days, Non-alcoholics 3.69 days, statistically significant p-value <0.05. Ventilator support Alcoholics 78.5%, Non-alcoholics 55%. Ventilatory duration Alcoholics 72.89 hours, Non-alcoholics 46.49 hours statistically significant p-value <0.05. **CONCLUSION:** Statistically significant relationship of Alcohol with Hypomagnesemia, severity of critical illness in terms of Duration of ICU Stay and Ventilation. Estimation of Serum Magnesium to be done in all critically ill patients with Alcohol consumption.

KEYWORDS: Alcohol Use Disorder, Serum Magnesium, Critically Ill, Severity, Apache Score

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INTRODUCTION

Social, pathological and medicinal uses of Alcohol have been a component of human tradition for thousands of years.¹ According to dietary guidelines “moderate” is considered to be an average of no more than two standard drinks per day for men and one standard drink per day in women not exceeding more than 3 drinks in any given day for women and 4 drinks for men poses a very low risk for developing an Alcohol Use Disorder (AUD).² An

AUD is an unhealthy pattern of alcohol use that causes significant clinical impairment and has been defined in DSM-V Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders-V to meet at least two of 11 specified Criteria. The total number

of criteria that are satisfied determines the severity, with two to three symptoms denoting a mild AUD, four to five signifying a moderate disorder and six or more representing a severe problem. DSM-V has abandoned the categorizations of “alcohol abuse” and “alcohol dependence” that were previously defined. While alcohol abuse and dependence represent different physiological effects of alcohol, for classification purposes these terms have been replaced with the single characterization of an AUD. Alcoholics are not only at increased risk for suffering critical illness but they also experience a greater likelihood of complications like increased risk and severity of sepsis, poorer outcomes and increased healthcare utilization. Chronic Alcohol

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consumption alters the oropharyngeal flora, impairs normal host defence mechanisms of the airway, impairs primary innate immune cell of lower airways, alveolar macrophages, which predisposes to lower respiratory tract infections and are at risk of ARDS, as pneumonia, sepsis, aspiration and traumatic injury are leading risk factors. AUDs have deleterious effects throughout the entire gastrointestinal system like Cirrhosis of liver, Oesophageal varices, Acute pancreatitis, Gastrointestinal haemorrhage, Peptic ulcer disease, mucosal erosions which are having profound impact on critical illness. AUDs are clinically prone to both myopathies and neuropathies.¹ Magnesium is the major intracellular divalent cation essential for normal neuromuscular activity, cellular function, replication and energy metabolism as it is an important cofactor for wide range of enzymes, transporters and nucleic acids. Normal Serum Magnesium ranges from 0.7 to 1 mmol/L (1.7 to 2.4 mg/dL) of which 30% is protein-bound and 15% is loosely complexed to phosphate and other anions. Total body Magnesium is mainly located in bone and intracellularly in mineral phase only 1% of body Magnesium resides in the Extra Cellular Fluid. Regulation of Magnesium is achieved mainly by control of renal Magnesium reabsorption as 20% of filtered Magnesium is reabsorbed in the proximal tubule, 60% in cortical thick ascending limb of Loop of Henle and 5–10% in the DCT.³ Alcoholics are more prone for Hypomagnesaemia due to malnutrition and affecting renal tubular absorption. Critical illness is a state of ill health with vital organ dysfunction, a high risk of imminent death if care is not provided and the potential for reversibility. Severity of critically illness is assessed by APACHE II (Acute Physiology and Chronic Health Evaluation II) introduced in 1985 a modification of the original APACHE developed in 1981. APACHE-II has three domains: Acute Physiology, Chronic Health Evaluation and Age reflected by the acronym APACHE. First domain relates with acute physiological changes within first 24 hours. Total maximum score will be 71 calculated as 12 physiological variables (12 x4), Temperature, Mean arterial blood pressure, Heart rate, Respiratory rate, Arterial oxygenation, Arterial pH, Serum sodium, Serum potassium, Serum Creatinine, Haematocrit, Total Leukocyte Count and GCS (0 to 12) and Chronic health problems (0 to 5) including severe organ insufficiency or immunocompromised and Age 4 (0 to 6)⁴. Critical illness polyneuropathy and myopathy are significant complications

of critical illness.⁵ This study was conducted as several studies across the world and from India highlighted the significant association of Magnesium and Alcohol with severity of critically illness in the form of adverse outcomes and mortality.^{6,7,8,9}

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Retrospective observational study conducted between January 2023 to June 2024 at a tertiary care centre, admitted under Department of General Medicine of Sri Siddhartha Medical College and Research Hospital, Tumakuru, Karnataka. Study was conducted after taking the clearance from the Institution Scientific and Ethical committee. Data collection done by using the case records from the Medical Records Department of the institution. All critically ill Patients of more than 18 years satisfying DSM-V guidelines for Alcohol Use Disorder, APACHE II score more than or equal to 10 were included in the study. APACHE II scoring was calculated using online software (<https://clinical.com/IcuMortality/APACHEI.aspx>). Patient details including Age, Sex, quantity and frequency of Alcohol consumption, APACHE II score, Serum Magnesium estimated by formazan dye method, Need for Ventilator support, Duration of ICU stay and Mortality were recorded in the prescribed proforma. Patients with Serum Magnesium less than 1.7 mg/dl were considered as Hypomagnesemia. Collected data was entered in Microsoft Excel sheet and analysed using SPSS software.

RESULTS

There were 118 critically ill patients between January 2023 to June 2024. There were 28 (23.7%) AUDs and 90 (76.2%) Non-Alcoholics who were considered as controls.

Age-wise distribution of Alcoholics and Non-Alcoholics

Age of Alcoholics ranges from 31 to 81 years with a Mean of 56.07 ± 13.08 years. Majority 28.5% were in 61-70 years age group followed by 21.4% in 41-50 years, 14.2% in 51-60 years and 71-80 years, 3.5% in >80 years and none in <30 years. Age of Non-Alcoholics ranges from 19 to 87 years with a Mean of 59.7 ± 15.5 years. Majority 26.6% were in the age group 61-70 years followed by 21.1% in 51-60 years and 71-80years, 7.7% in <30 years and 4.4% in >80 years group. **Table 1. Fig 1.**

Table 1. Age-wise distribution of Alcoholics and Non-Alcoholics

Age group	Alcoholics N (%)	Non-alcoholics N (%)
<30 Years	0 (0%)	7 (7.7%)
30-40 Years	5 (17.8%)	4 (4.4%)
41-50 Years	6 (21.4%)	13 (14.4%)

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51-60 Years	4 (14.2%)	19 (21.1%)
61-70 Years	8 (28.5%)	24 (26.6%)
71-80 Years	4 (14.2%)	19 (21.1%)
>80 Years	1 (3.5%)	4 (4.4%)
Total	28	90

Fig 1. Age-wise distribution of Alcoholics and Non-Alcoholics
Gender wise distribution Alcoholics and Non-Alcoholics

Majority Alcoholics were Male 22 (78.5%) and 6 (21.4%) were Females. Majority Non-Alcoholics were also Male 48 (53.3%) and 42 (46.6%) were Female. **Table 2. Fig 2.**

Table 2. Gender wise distribution Alcoholics and Non-Alcoholics

Gender	Alcoholics N (%)	Non-Alcoholics N (%)
Male	22 (78.5%)	48 (53.3%)
Female	6 (21.4%)	42 (46.6%)
Total	28 (23.7%)	90 (76.2%)

Fig 2. Gender wise distribution Alcoholics and Non-Alcoholics
Etiological distribution of critically ill patients

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Critically ill patients had multisystem involvements with variable primary system involvement, predominantly 10 respiratory in origin, followed by 5 Hepatic, 3 each in cardiac renal and gastrointestinal, 2 each in neurologic and fluid electrolyte disorders. **Table 3.**

Table 3. Etiological distribution of critically ill patients

System involved	Alcoholics N (%)	Non-alcoholics N (%)
Respiratory	10	31
Hepatic	5	2
Renal	3	15
Cardiac	3	26
Gastrointestinal	3	2
Fluid/electrolyte imbalance	2	6
Neurological	2	8
Total	28	90

Hypomagnesemia in Alcoholics and Non-Alcoholics

Hypomagnesaemia was observed in 38 (32.2%), Normomagneseemia was observed in 69 (58.4%) in critically ill patients. Hypomagnesaemia was observed in 19 (67.8%), Normomagneseemia was observed in 6 (21.4%) in Alcoholics.

Hypomagnesaemia was observed in 19(21.1%) and Normomagneseemia observed in 63 (70%) in Non-Alcoholics. Hypomagneseemia in Alcoholics is having highly statistically significant relation with Non-Alcoholics with p-value <0.001. **Table 4. Fig 3.**

Table 4. Hypomagneseemia in Alcoholics and Non-Alcoholics

Serum Mg	Alcoholics N (%)	Non-Alcoholics N (%)	P-value <0.001
Low	19 (67.8%)	19 (21.1%)	
Normal	6 (21.4%)	63 (70%)	
High	3 (10.7%)	8 (8.8%)	
Total	28	90	

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Fig 3. Hypomagnesemia in Alcoholics and Non-Alcoholics
Mean APACHE II in Alcoholics and Non-Alcoholics

APACHE II score ranged from 12 to 44 in Alcoholics with Mean of 23.5 ± 6.88 compared to 10 to 49 in Non-Alcoholics with Mean of 21.08 ± 7.4 . APACHE II score in Alcoholics

and Non-Alcoholics is not statistically significant. **Table 5. Fig 4.**

Table 5. Mean APACHE II in Alcoholics and Non-Alcoholics

APACHE II score	Alcoholics N (%)	Non-Alcoholics N (%)
Minimum	12	10
Maximum	44	49
Mean \pm SD	23.5 ± 6.8	21.08 ± 7.4

Fig 4. Mean APACHE II in Alcoholics and Non-Alcoholics

DURATION OF ICU STAY

Duration of ICU stay in Alcoholics ranged from 1 to 11 days with Mean Duration of 4.75 ± 2.52 Days. Duration of ICU

stay in Non-Alcoholics ranged from 1 to 11 days with Mean Duration of 3.69 ± 2.17 Days. Duration of ICU stay was more in Alcoholics suggesting strong association in duration

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of ICU stay between Alcoholics and Non-Alcoholics as it is statistically significant with p-value of <0.05. **Table 6.**

Table 6. Duration of ICU stay

Duration of ICU stay	Alcoholics N (%)	Non-Alcoholics N (%)	P-value <0.05
Mean \pm SD	4.75 \pm 2.52	3.69 \pm 2.17	
Range	1-11	1-11	

Need for Ventilator

Need for Ventilator is more in Alcoholics 22 (78.5%) compared to Non-Alcoholics 50 (55%). There was association in Need for Ventilator between Alcoholics and Non-Alcoholics but it is statistically not significant with p-value of 1.0. **Table 7.**

Table 7. Need for Ventilator

Category	Need for ventilator	P-value 1.0
Alcoholics	22 (78.5%)	
Non-Alcoholics	50 (55%)	

Duration of Ventilation

Duration of Ventilation in Alcoholics ranged from 0 to 240 hours with Mean Duration of 72.89 \pm 63.88 hours. Duration of Ventilation in Non-Alcoholics ranged from 0 to 216 hours with Mean Duration of 46.49 \pm 57.33 hours. Duration of

ventilation was more in Alcoholics suggesting association in duration of ventilation between Alcoholics and Non-Alcoholics as it is statistically significant with p-value of <0.05. **Table 8.**

Table 8. Duration of Ventilation

Duration of Ventilation	Alcoholics N (%)	Non-Alcoholics N (%)	P-value <0.05
Mean \pm SD	72.89 \pm 63.88	46.49 \pm 57.33	
Range	0-240	0-216	

Hypomagnesemia and Morbidity outcome in Alcoholics and Non-Alcoholics

Hypomagnesemia have higher morbidity in terms of Mean Duration of ICU stay, Need and duration of ventilator.

Hypomagnesemia in Alcoholics is having statistically significant association with Duration of ICU stay and Duration of ventilator but, having statistically not significant association with need of ventilator. **Table 9.**

Table 9. Hypomagnesemia and Morbidity outcome in Alcoholics and Non-Alcoholics

Morbidity outcomes in Hypomagnesemia	Alcoholics	Non-Alcoholics	P-value
Mean Duration of ICU stay	4.75 days	3.69 days	<0.05
Mean Duration of Ventilation	72.89 hours	46.49 hours	<0.05
Need for Ventilation	78.5%	50%	1.0

DISCUSSION

Alcohol use disorders not only predispose individuals to develop critical illness, but also leave these vulnerable patients with longer ICU stays, more complications and ultimately greater mortality. There were 23.7% Alcoholics

compared to 76.3% Non-Alcoholics in this study which was comparable to 36.3% Alcoholics and 63.7% Non-Alcoholics in diabetes by Kiran et al⁸, comparable to 36.3% Alcoholics and 63.7% Non-Alcoholics in diabetes by Waheed et al⁹. Age and Sex is similar in both groups in this study as Mean age in

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Alcoholics is 56.07 and 59.7 in Non-Alcoholics. Majority belongs to age group of 61 to 70 years in both Alcoholics (28.5%) and Non-Alcoholics(26.6%) comparable to 45 to 55 years by Waheed et al⁹. There was male preponderance of 78.5% in Alcoholics compared to 53.3% in Non-Alcoholics. There was Hypomagnesemia in 67.8% of Alcoholics comparable to 45% by Waheed et al⁹, 34.7% by Vineesha et al¹⁰, 60% by Kumar et al¹¹, 50% by Limaya et al¹², 34% by Soliman et al¹³. This relation between Hypomagnesemia and Alcohol is highly statistically significant with p-value of <0.001. Mean APACHE II score in Hypomagnesemic is 27.07 comparable with 23.6% by Solanki et al⁶, 27.8% by Gupta et al¹⁴ and Hypomagnesemic Non-Alcoholics 19.1. Mean APACHE II in Alcoholics is 23.5 compared to 21 in Non-Alcoholics in our study. APACHE II score in Alcoholics and Non-alcoholics is not statistically significant. Alcoholics has more morbidity in terms of more duration of ICU stay of 4.75 days comparable with 4.85 days by Kongara et al¹⁵, 6.2 days by Solanki et al⁶ and 3.69 days in Non-Alcoholics which was statistically significant as p-value <0.05. Need for Ventilator in Alcoholics was more 78.5% comparable with 74.5% by Ugaragol et al⁷, 73% by Limaye et al¹² and Kumar et al¹¹ and 55% in Non-Alcoholics but not statistically significant. Duration of Ventilatory support of 72.89 hours in Alcoholics compared to 46.49 hours in Non-Alcoholics which is also statistically significant as p-value is <0.05. Alcohol have higher morbidity in terms of Mean Duration of ICU stay, Need and duration of ventilator. Alcoholics is having statistically significant association with Duration of ICU stay and Duration of ventilator but, having statistically not significant association with need of ventilator. Relation between Alcohol and severity of critical illness is statistically significant as p-value <0.05 in terms of both Duration of ICU stay and Duration of ventilation. There was no statistical significant association between Alcohol and Non-Alcoholics with Mean APACHE II score and Need for Ventilator. Hypomagnesemia have higher morbidity in terms of Mean Duration of ICU stay, Need and duration of ventilator. Hypomagnesemia in Alcoholics is having statistically significant association with Duration of ICU stay and Duration of ventilator but, having statistically not significant association with need of ventilator.

CONCLUSION

Alcohol is one of the commonest risk factor in critically ill patient. Prevalence of Hypomagnesemia is also common in Alcoholics. Hypomagnesemic Alcoholics has more morbidity in terms of more duration of ICU stay and duration of ventilation. Alcohol Use Disorder can be kept in mind as a major risk factor in assessing the severity of illness in critically ill patients as Hypomagnesemia is more prevalent in Alcoholics. Magnesium has to be assessed in all Alcoholics. Critical care providers should better evaluate their patients for Alcohol Use Disorder and their potential implications.

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